

Vanadium(V) Complexes of N-cinnamoyl-N-*o*-methoxyphenylhydroxylamine and N-cinnamoyl-N-*p*-methylphenylhydroxylamine. Its Determination in Alloy Steels and Rock Samples

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N-cinnamoyl-N-*o*-methoxyphenylhydroxylamine(I) and N-cinnamoyl-N-*p*-methylphenylhydroxylamine (II) form complexes of vanadium(V), bluish violet in color and extractable into chloroform, having λ_{max} at 530 nm and 550 nm with metal to ligand ratio of 1:2 in the acidity range 2.5 (with I) and 1.5N HCl (with II). Beer's law is obeyed over 1-14 ppm and 0.4-14 ppm of vanadium with optimum concentration ranges of 2-10 ppm and 1.4-10 ppm for complexes of I and II respectively, the % relative error is 2.70 and 2.72 for the complexes, the molar absorptivities (ϵ) are 6000 and 5900 $l.mol^{-1}cm^{-1}$ while the sensitivities are 0.0085 and 0.0086 $\mu g V/cm^2$ respectively.

The extraction constant, K_{ex} , is evaluated from the intercept of the Hiskey-Meloche's plot. A spectrophotometric method based on solvent extraction technique, for the trace analysis of vanadium(V) in presence of diverse ions, in alloy steels and rock samples, has also been described.

EXTENSIVE investigations on the spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(V) have shown that the most sensitive spectrophotometric reagents for the metal are the various disubstituted aromatic hydroxylamine. N-BPHA has been extensively used as a reagent for the solvent extraction and spectrophotometric determination of vanadium^{1,2} and for its direct determination in steels³, alloys, ores¹, blood, urine and plant products and other complex materials⁴. The most sensitive and selective derivatives claimed by various authors are: N-benzoyl-*o*-tolyl⁵ ($\epsilon = 4745$), N-cinnamoyl-N-phenyl⁶ ($\epsilon = 6000$), N-*p*-methoxybenzoyl-N-*m*-tolyl⁷ ($\epsilon = 5750$), N-2-thenocarbonyl-N-*o*-methoxyphenyl⁸ ($\epsilon = 7200$) and N-3-styrylacrylcarbonyl-N-phenyl-hydroxylamine⁹ ($\epsilon = 7500$).

Present studies have shown that both reagents N-cinnamoyl-N-*o*-methoxyphenyl- (I) and N-cinnamoyl-*p*-methylphenylhydroxylamine(II)¹⁰, are also sensitive and can be deployed for the analysis of alloy steels and rock samples without prior separation of cations present. Both the reagents I and II form bluish violet complexes ($\epsilon = 6000$ with I and 5900 with II) with vanadium(V) in strongly acid medium (2.5M HCl) and the species are selectively extracted into chloroform and the color intensity of the complexes are found to remain stable for more than 48 hrs at room temperature. The Beer's law and optimum ranges are 1.0-14 ppm and 0.4-14 ppm, 2-10 ppm and 1.4-10 ppm with both I and II respectively. The composition of the metal : reagent is 1:2 in both the cases. The stepwise stability values calculated, following Leden's and Yatsimirskii's methods, appear more or less of the same order for the complexes. So it can be concluded that the two bidentate chelating groups attach to vanadium simultaneously.

Like other derivatives of hydroxylamines both the reagents I and II also suffer interference from Ti (IV), Mo(VI), W(VI) but with higher tolerance limit for last two ions than other reagents. The interference of Ti(IV) can be removed with fluoride as the masking agent. The reliability of the reagents has been confirmed from their application to the analysis of vanadium containing standard alloy steels and rock samples.

Experimental

Preparation of Reagents: Reagents N-cinnamoyl-N-*o*-methoxyphenylhydroxylamine(I) and N-cinnamoyl-N-*p*-methylphenylhydroxylamine(II) were prepared from *o*-nitroanisole and *p*-nitrotoluene and cinnamoyl chloride according to the procedure described in the literature¹¹. The crude reagent, I, a sticky mass, was crystallised from alcohol and acetone. The m.p. of the white needle shaped crystals of reagent I and yellowish needle shaped crystals of reagent II are 100° and 163° respectively. The analysis of the compounds, indicates the formulae of the compound to be $C_{16}H_{15}O_3N$ (I) and $C_{16}H_{15}O_2N$ (II). Standard reagent solutions of desired strength in A.R. chloroform were used. A standard stock solution of vanadium(V) was prepared from A.R. ammonium meta vanadate and it was standardised for vanadium content volumetrically¹².

Doubly distilled water was used whenever necessary. Other chemicals used in all spectrophotometric measurements were of A.R. or spectrograde quality.

General Extraction Procedure for Vanadium (V): An aliquot (1ml of $1.965 \times 10^{-3} M$) of the metal solution was transferred to a separatory funnel (100 ml) and

the acidity of the solution was adjusted using 6*N* HCl solution. Extractions were carried out with equal volume of aqueous to non-aqueous phase (15 ml) by adding required volume of particular reagent, solvent and water. The mixture was then shaken for 5 min and the intense bluish violet chloroform extract was drained out in a 50 ml beaker and dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The dried chloroform extract was transferred to 25 ml calibrated flask. The aqueous layer was further shaken with 5 ml chloroform, extracted and dried as before and then collected in the same flask and finally diluted upto the mark with chloroform. The absorbance of the solution was then measured on a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer at 530 nm and at 550 nm (respective λ_{max} of I and II) against solvent as blank.

Evaluation of metal-reagent ratio of the complex : Following the well known distribution method of Hiskey and Meloche¹³, and developed further by other workers^{14,15}, the average number of ligands bound to the vanadyl ion was established to be 2 and the log K_{st} computed by the graphical method.

Results and Discussion

Absorption Spectrum : The absorption spectra of the colored system in chloroform obtained with reagents I and II was measured in the wavelength region 400 nm to 620 nm against chloroform as blank. The spectral curves show that V(V) complex with reagent I absorb maximum at 530 nm and with reagent II at 550 nm where the reagents possess no absorption.

Effect of acidity : The intensity of the colored V(V) complexes was found to be maximum at the overall acid concentration of 2-5*N* and 1-5*N* with reagents I and II respectively. Increase of acid concentration results in the decrease of color intensity.

Effect of reagent concentration : 5.0 ml of 0.5% (w/v) solution of reagent I and of 0.1% (w/v) solution of reagent II in chloroform is sufficient for maximum color development of V(V) (4 ppm) complex at the particular acidity. Addition of more reagent had no effect.

Calibration curve, optimum range and photometric error of the complexes : The colored systems obeyed Beer's law from 1-14 ppm and 0.4-14 ppm at 4*N* and 2*N* HCl with reagents I and II respectively at λ_{max} .

To evaluate optimum range and analytical accuracy, Ringbom's¹⁶ curves were drawn by plotting % absorbance as ordinate against log concentration of metal as abscissa. The optimum concentration range with the highest accuracy for V(V)-reagent I complex is from 2-10 ppm and for reagent II complex is from 1.4-10 ppm.

The percent relative error per 1% absolute photometric error was calculated according to the Ayres¹⁷

equation and was found to be 2.70 and 2.72 for I and II systems respectively.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity : The molar absorptivity values for the complexes were calculated from Beer's law data and are found to be 6000 and 5900 L.mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ for V(V) complexes with I and II. Corresponding to the Sandell¹⁸ sensitivities of 0.00354 $\mu\text{g V/cm}^2$ and 0.00862 $\mu\text{g V/cm}^2$ respectively.

Effect of diverse ions : To study the effect due to other ions, solutions with varying concentrations of different diverse ions were prepared with reagents (I and II as the case may be) following the general procedure described earlier and 4 ppm of vanadium (V). It was observed that it suffered interferences mainly from Ti(IV), Mo(VI), W(VI), Nb(V) and Zr(IV) but with higher tolerance limits. Interference due to Ti(IV) can be avoided using NaF in excess as a masking agent. Interference due to Mo(VI) can be removed by ethyl xanthate-extraction¹⁹.

Tolerance limits of the ions in ppm are shown within brackets. Citrate (1000), oxalate (1000), tartrate (500), F⁻ (1000), EDTA (1000), PO₄⁻³ (1000), acetate (1000), Al³⁺ (200), Be²⁺ (200), Mg²⁺ (200), Ba²⁺ (200), Zn²⁺ (200), Sr²⁺ (200), Pb²⁺ (200), Hg²⁺ (150), Cd²⁺ (200), As³⁺ (150), Fe³⁺ (200), Co²⁺ (200), Ni²⁺ (200), Cr³⁺ (200), Mn²⁺ (200), In³⁺ (200), UO₂²⁺ (200), Ti⁴⁺ (S.I)^{*}, MoO₄⁻² (50), W⁶⁺ (80), Th⁴⁺ (200), Nb⁵⁺ (20), Ta⁵⁺ (20), Zr⁴⁺ (60).

Procedure for the analysis of High Speed Steel (BAS 64b-containing 1.99% V) : The sample (0.6 g) was dissolved in dilute (1:4) sulphuric acid and it was evaporated to a syrupy mass on a hot plate. The process was repeated twice with 5 ml of the acid each time. Finally, the solution was treated with an excess (5 ml) of concentrated sulphuric acid followed by 2 ml of concentrated nitric acid. The solution was evaporated slowly in a fuming chamber till the evolution of free SO₂ fumes. It was then cooled and diluted to about 50 ml with doubly distilled water. The solution was warmed to dissolve any undissolved solid matter and filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper. The residue was washed several times with hot water. The filtrate and washings were collected and the volume made upto 250 ml.

An aliquot of the above solution was oxidised in hot by the addition of dilute potassium permanganate solution. The vanadium content was determined following the general extraction procedure. The percentage of vanadium in the sample was found to be 1.98% with I and 1.97% with II.

Procedure for Rock Analysis : Determination of vanadium in Ilmenite and other different samples : Transfer finely powdered sample of ilmenite (Hornbendite rock, contains 0.1% vanadium) (1.0 g) in a silica crucible. Fuse with potassium bisulphate (5.0 g) for first decomposition, continue after the addition of

*S. I.—seriously interferes.

another 5.0 g potassium bisulphate till the sample completely decomposed. Cool the melt and leach with (1+9) sulphuric acid in 250ml beaker and this is heated nearly to boiling. Neutralise the solution of the decomposed sample, and concentrate to a small volume. Excess titanium and iron in the samples are reduced by precipitating as hydroxides by treating with dilute ammonia (1 : 1). Filter into another beaker by careful washing with minimum quantity of hot water. Any vanadium adsorbed on the hydroxides is recovered by reprecipitation. The two filtrates are combined and concentrated to about 50 ml by evaporation. Acidify to litmus with dilute sulphuric acid and make up the volume of the solution to 100 ml in volumetric flask.

Transfer 10 ml of aliquot of this solution to a 100 ml beaker. Oxidise vanadium in hot by adding 0.1% potassium permanganate solution until the pink color persists. Determine the vanadium content in the solution following the general procedure by adding excess ammonium fluoride (~0.2 g) at 4N HCl. Then calculate the percentage of vanadium in the sample. The results of a few analysed samples using reagent are given in table 1.

TABLE 1—RESULTS ON ANALYSED SAMPLES

Sample	Percentage of Vanadium Found	Percentage of Vanadium Reported
1. *Ilmenite (Hornblendite rock, Kavur Anchal, Tamilnadu, India)	0.098	0.1
2. Ilmenite (collected from Indian Oxygen Ltd., Calcutta)	0.124	0.130
3. Ilmenite*, IGS-31 (London)	0.065	0.062
4. Magnetite* (Titaniferrous Magnetite)-TM, GSI, Calcutta.	1.02	1.05

*Collected from G.S.I., Calcutta.

Composition of the complexes: The composition of the complexes with reagents I and II have been found to be 1:2 by applying Job's^{20,21} and molar ratio²² methods. These are further verified from the graphical plot of log (Distribution coefficient) vs. log [reagent]_{org} - pH of Hiskey-Meloche's method¹³⁻¹⁵.

Evaluation of Stability and Equilibrium Extraction constants: The stepwise stability constants were calculated following the extended Yatsimirskii's²³ and Leden's^{24,25} methods.

The degree of dissociation, α and overall stability constants K_{ov} , were further verified by Harvey and Manning's method²⁶. The equilibrium extraction constants, K_{ex} for the complexes were obtained from extrapolation of distribution method. The different values of stability constants along with equilibrium extraction constants are given in Table 2.

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TABLE 2—STEPWISE AND OVERALL STABILITY AND EXTRACTION CONSTANTS FOR V(V)-REAGENTS (I AND II) COMPLEX SYSTEMS AT 27°C

	Leden's Method			Yatsimirskii's Method			Harvey-Manning's Method	Extraction constant (Hiskey-Meloche's method) log K_{ex}
	log K_1	log K_2	log K	log K_1	log K_2	log K	log K	
1. V(V)-I system	4.32	4.28	8.60	4.63	4.14	8.77	8.93	8.80
2. V(V)-II system	3.81	3.77	7.58	3.90	3.53	7.43	7.94	7.60

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